

Coherent Multi-Dimensional Spectroscopy Reveals Homogeneous Lineshape Dynamics in CsPbBr₃ Quantum Dots

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Abstract

Lead Halide Perovskite (LHP) Quantum Dots (QD) are an attractive material for light emissive applications due to their lattice which is both dynamically disordered and defect tolerant. Development of LHP QD for quantum emitters critically depends on characterization of their homogeneous lineshapes. Homogeneous lineshapes are measured by single dot photoluminescence spectroscopy only at cryogenic temperatures for which their lattice dynamics are frozen out. There are presently no experiments which reveal the lineshapes at 300K, let alone their dynamics due to lattice fluctuations. Here we perform Coherent Multi-Dimensional Spectroscopy (CMDS) on a broad size range of CsPbBr₃ QD at 300K to observe homogeneous lineshapes and their dynamics on the femtosecond timescale of lattice motions. Contrasting to linear spectroscopies, these nonlinear CMDS experiments unambiguously reveal that the room temperature homogeneous linewidths are both narrow and size independent at 300K. The ensuing femtosecond lineshape dynamics is governed by size dependent exciton-lattice interactions. These results demonstrate the potential LHP QD for high temperature quantum light sources.

Keywords: lead halide perovskite, quantum dot, nanocrystal, homogeneous linewidth, lineshape dynamics, coherent multi-dimensional spectroscopy, two-dimensional electronic spectroscopy

Introduction and Motivation

The lineshape of an optical transition reflects the electronic properties of a material and arises from coupling between the electrons and the lattice¹⁻³. In the case of semiconductor quantum dots (QD)⁴, the electronic system is comprised of excitons, for which each excitonic state couples to the phonon bath⁵⁻⁷, giving rise to spectral line broadening by system-bath interactions⁸. In contrast, most pictures of QD invoke only electronic states, resulting in their being described as two-level systems⁴. To this date much of the optics and electronic structure of QD only focuses on excitons as a level system, absent of coupling to lattice modes. Hence there is tremendous need for unraveling how lattice structure and dynamics dresses the electronic and thus optical response of QD.

The lineshape of an excitonic optical transition in a QD is of paramount importance to their deployment in optoelectronic devices⁹⁻¹⁵. In the simplest case of light emitting diodes, the historic aim was to exploit the narrow spectral lines of QD to make saturated colors for better rendering of color. However, broad spectral lines enabled by strong exciton-phonon coupling can be a path to create white light¹⁶. For QD lasers, narrow lines enable greater efficiency, whereas broad lines due to exciton-phonon coupling can enable both short pulses and spectral tunability. In recent efforts to make quantum light sources¹⁷⁻²² a key figure of merit is the pure dephasing timescale relative to the population decay timescale, $T_2^* / 2T_1$. As QD move from classical to quantum light sources, unraveling the physics of broadening of the spectral lines of the excitonic system by the lattice bath becomes still more crucial²³.

A recently developed material for classical and quantum light sources is lead halide perovskite (LHP) quantum dots (QD)^{14, 19, 20, 24-27}. These LHP QD are remarkable in that they have many favorable optical properties despite strong exciton-lattice coupling to a dynamically disordered lattice²⁸⁻³¹. This unique lattice is known to be defect tolerant^{32, 33} due to the shallow nature of the present defect states, ensured by antibonding nature of the conduction and valence bands. Their low frequency spectral density of phonons has been shown to confer liquid-solid duality as a phonon glass electron crystal^{8, 30, 34-39}. However, the same strong coupling to the soft and disordered lattice should also promote dephasing thereby preventing the deployment of LHP QD as quantum emitters.

The conventional means to characterize homogenous lineshapes is single QD photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy^{19, 20, 40-44}. Single QD PL circumvents inhomogeneous broadening to reveal the homogeneous spectrum of a single QD. The challenge is that these PL experiments are possible only at cryogenic temperatures, limiting their ability to characterize lineshapes above 150K⁴⁴ let alone at room temperature. More specifically, the single QD PL experiments cannot report on the lineshape broadening processes that take place on the femtosecond timescale of the intrinsic lattice response³⁷.

Here we employ the unique capacity of coherent multi-dimensional spectroscopy^{1, 2, 45-47} (CMDS) to bypass the limitations of single QD PL, reporting on the interactions which govern homogeneous optical lineshapes and their dynamics in a wide size range of CsPbBr₃ LHP QD. These broadband CMDS experiments reveal that the homogenous lineshapes are both narrow and size independent at 300K. The size independence of the homogenous lineshapes contrasts to the strong size dependent total linewidths. Following the dynamics of the homogenous

lineshapes, the lattice fluctuations which give rise to total linewidths are characterized. The evolution from homogenous lineshapes to total lineshapes takes place on the 100 fs timescale, revealing how fluctuations give rise to line broadening in LHP QD. These CMDS experiments on LHP QD reveal their broad applicability for quantum emitters at elevated temperatures, as well as providing a pathway for future materials development for designer emitters.

Results and Discussion

Fig1 presents an overview of the question of excitonic lineshapes in LHP QD. Like all QD, LHP QD ensembles have size, shape, and composition inhomogeneity which gives rise to static lineshape broadening. **Fig1a** shows a transmission electron microscope (TEM) image of 18 nm diameter CsPbBr₃ QD. Details of the synthesis are found in our prior works^{24, 48} and in the Supplementary Information (SI). **Fig1b** shows the histogram of diameters in a typical synthesis. **Fig1c** shows the lattice structure of these LHP QD, which exhibit an orthorhombic crystal structure at room temperature. **Fig1d** illustrates the way in which the exciton couples to the lattice, via polarons in LHP QD^{8, 37, 49, 50}.

The linear spectroscopy of these LHP QD is summarized in **Fig2a**. Shown are linear absorption and PL spectra at 300 K of weakly confined (18 nm diameter) and strongly confined (5.9 nm diameter) QD. The exciton Bohr diameter is 7 nm. The largest QD are sufficiently weakly confined that they may be considered bulk-like nanocrystals (NC). While these bulk-like NC should not show QD like effects, they still do^{8, 50-54} for reasons that remain unclear. On this question, of QD vs NC, we have recently written in light of spectroscopic measurables⁵⁵. The key observation

is the linewidths, which are 76 and 112 meV full width at half maximum (FWHM). Historically, broad QD linewidths have been assigned to broad size distributions arising from poor synthetic control. In contrast to this historic view, which is incorrect, we have reported on broad linewidths arising from strong coupling to lattice phonons⁵⁶⁻⁶³, a point that could be exploited in optical applications^{16, 56}.

To demonstrate that these linewidth variations are systematic rather than random, **Fig2b** shows the size dependent FWHM of the PL. There is a strong size dependence to the peak width, with smaller QD showing larger widths. We stress the importance of quantitative analysis of linewidths should be done in energy (or frequency) units for the sake of linearity. As well, the PL spectrum should be properly transformed from nm to eV⁶⁴. In an ensemble averaged linear spectroscopic experiment, it is impossible to quantify the homogeneous, inhomogeneous, and lattice contributions to linewidths, let alone their dynamics.

An enabling step past ensemble linear spectroscopy has been single QD PL spectroscopy^{44, 48, 65, 66} to quantify the static inhomogeneous line broadening. These measurements are possible at only cryogenic temperatures, (4 – 150 K). Moreover, single QD PL can only capture energy fluctuations on the slow timescale of ms – s, the timescale of the environment which hosts the QD. But single QD PL fails to capture spectral diffusion on the intrinsic timescale of the lattice fluctuations^{30, 31, 34, 37, 38, 67}. Indeed, single QD PL experiments on these samples at 150 K⁴⁴ show exactly the same linewidths as in the ensembles shown here, demonstrating that that single QD PL is unable to capture the relevant lineshape broadening processes.

Whereas there are fundamental limitations to linear spectroscopic measurements of optical linewidths, non-linear spectroscopy excels at this task. The ways in which nonlinear spectroscopy, specifically four-wave mixing (FWM) implemented as Coherent Multi-Dimensional Spectroscopy (CMDS) have been discussed in detail^{1-3, 46, 68}. To make the transition to nonlinear spectroscopy one must move from photon absorption and emission to field-matter interactions. Specific field-matter interactions give rise to linear and nonlinear polarizations. These polarizations undergo the optical equivalent of free induction decay (FID) as free polarization decay (FPD). While FID is more commonly used in CMDS⁶⁹, FPD is the correct term for the process.

Fig3a shows the macroscopic polarization and thus signal field that is generated in an ensemble of quantum two-level systems. Simple phenomenological theory decomposes the total dephasing time, T_2 , into contributions from excited state lifetime, T_1 , and pure dephasing, T_2^* . We begin with these phenomenological limits before moving to a generalized microscopic theory of lineshape dynamics^{1 2, 3, 46, 70}. Shown on top is the FID / FPD based upon total dephasing, T_2 . Shown in the middle is the same total dephasing with inclusion of inhomogeneous distribution of quantum states, for example due to size inhomogeneity in QDs. Shown on the bottom is the FID with inclusion of spectral diffusion as described coupling to a broad spectral density of phonons, consistent with expectations for LHP QD at 300 K. **Fig3b** shows the corresponding lineshapes by Fourier transformation of the FID / FPD. The top is a Lorentzian, the middle is a Voigt, whereas the bottom is neither limit but must be simulated to obtain.

Fig3 further illustrates moving beyond phenomenological dephasing models and observe these long sought spectral dynamics by moving from linear to nonlinear CMDS. The key concept is illustrated in **Fig3c**. The exciton can be modeled as a two-level system with energy difference

ΔE_{x1} . The excited state lifetime T_1 acts as an upper limit for the coherence time. In realistic condensed matter systems, fluctuations in the environment cause the energy gap to fluctuate. The dynamical fluctuation $\delta E(t)$ are the dominant source of dephasing in most cases, and their statistics determine the exact dephasing dynamics and spectral lineshape. We have previously shown on one diameter of LHP QD that these dynamics are overdamped and diffusive³⁷, which was assigned to polaron formation dynamics that are viewed to be central to the physics and function of LHP^{30, 31, 35, 36, 38, 39, 50, 67, 71-74}

Fig3d illustrates the specific model we apply to LHP QD; the overdamped Brownian oscillator^{3 46, 70}. It consists of a quantum exciton (the system) interacting with a classical lattice (the bath). On a configuration coordinate diagram, the system has a parabolic potential energy surface (PES) with identical curvature for the ground and excited state. The system-bath coupling arises from the different minima of the two PES along the lattice coordinate. Following photoexcitation, the system undergoes dynamics on the excited state potential energy surface under the action of 3 forces: the harmonic potential, damping (dissipation) and random thermal perturbations (fluctuations).

Fig4a illustrates how these dynamics ensue, as one moves from single QD trajectories to the ensemble average. Shown are single QD energy fluctuation trajectories for identical initial conditions, and the average behavior described by the correlation function. The individual trajectories never decay, and they continuously to undergo erratic oscillations. In the overdamped case, the damping and fluctuations desynchronize the ensemble faster than the oscillation period. The energy-energy correlation function $C(t) = \langle \delta E(t) \delta E(0) \rangle / \hbar^2$, describing the ensemble behavior, decays with timescale τ as the individual trajectories become unsynchronized.

Fig4b shows the distributions of energies of the single QD trajectories from the previous panel. At early times, the distribution is sharply peaked around the initial excitation energy. However, due to the fluctuations from the environment, the distribution both shifts towards the average value and broadens. To fully capture these dynamics, it is necessary to use a method which can measure the energy-energy time-correlation function. To measure these energy fluctuations and their correlations, one must move from linear spectroscopy, even single QD PL spectroscopy, to femtosecond nonlinear spectroscopy. In particular, CMDS^{1, 2, 3, 46}, is uniquely able to measure these quantities of great interest that have never been observed in QD.

Fig4c shows a three-pulse sequence used in these CMDS experiments. Pulse 1 arrives at time zero, exciting the system into a coherence which corresponds to linear absorption. The coherence oscillates at the excitation energy E_1 . Pulse 2 arrives second and further excites the system from a coherence to a population, which undergoes dynamics. In the current case, those are fluctuations and dissipation due to the soft lattice. Pulse 3 arrives last, exciting the system from a population to a coherence, which oscillates at the detection frequency E_3 . The resulting 2D spectra correlate the excitation energy E_1 with the detection energy E_3 , as a function of a population time t_2 . These points are discussed in reviews of CMDS^{1, 2, 3, 46} and in the **SI**, and in our prior CMDS works^{37, 49, 69, 75-82}.

In CMDS of LHP QD, a key challenge is to obtain pump spectra with broad bandwidths (~ 100 meV) at blue photon energies (2.5 eV). Our methods to overcome these challenges are described in detail in prior works^{37, 49, 78, 79, 83} and in the **SI**. CMDS with suitably short blue pulses therefore enable the direct measurements^{49, 75, 76} of the fluctuations in the ensemble due to the soft lattice and can directly be interpreted in terms of correlation functions.

Fig5 illustrates how CMDS reveals the lineshape dynamics arising from lattice fluctuations. Shown in **Fig5a**-bare schematic linear absorption spectra of an inhomogeneously broadened ensemble of QD, each having some homogeneous broadening. There is inhomogeneous distribution of homogeneous lineshapes giving rise to a Voigt lineshape. But these spectra must be obtained at a point in time prior to any lattice dynamics that may give rise to lineshape dynamics. **Fig5b** shows the ensemble following lattice dynamics. The ensemble lineshape may look the same but clearly sub-ensembles interchanged states. A more detailed discussion is enabled by simulations.

Fig5c-d show simulated CMDS spectra obtained using the cumulant expansion to second order, as detailed in the **SI**. This method enables the modeling of the absorption and CMDS spectra corresponding to a specific microscopic fluctuation. According to this model, the polarization oscillates at the frequency corresponding to the energy gap and decays as $\exp[-g(t)]$ where $g(t) = \int_0^t d\tau \int_0^\tau d\tau' C(\tau')$ is a complex function of time, the lineshape function. The duration of the coherence is therefore uniquely determined by $g(t)$, which is obtained directly from $C(t)$. (**see SI**). Using the cumulant expansion, we can therefore model the dephasing associated with microscopic models of dephasing and therefore go beyond the empirical dephasing rate models with fixed T_2^{*20} .

Our picture of dephasing in LHP QDs has two contributions: a dynamic part due to the lattice bath, and a static inhomogeneous part due to size inhomogeneity: $g(t) = g_D(t) + g_S(t)$ (**see SI**). For the dynamic contribution, we use the overdamped Brownian oscillator which is characterized by three parameters: the fluctuation amplitude σ , the correlation time τ and the temperature^{3, 70}. The static contribution is given by the standard deviation σ_S of the transition

energies. These 3 parameters are sufficient to reproduce the experimental lineshape dynamics in LHP QDs.

Fig5c-d shows the absorptive 2D spectra obtained using this model at $t_2=20$ and 800 fs. We designate 20 fs as early time (prior to lattice dynamics) and 800 fs (after lattice dynamics) based both upon prior knowledge of spectral diffusion in LHP QD^{37, 49} and their low frequency spectral density^{8, 30, 38, 84}. These numbers are confirmed as suitably early and late by experimental data. At early times (**Fig3c**), the spectrum is elongated along the diagonal. The 2D spectra can be interpreted as a correlation map between excitation energies (E_1) and detection energies (E_3). The diagonal elongation therefore indicates that the frequencies of the individual QD did not shift much during the $t_2=20$ fs evolution period. The peak is significantly narrower along the anti-diagonal (red dashed line) than along the diagonal (black dashed line). Due to the coupling to a broad phonon distribution at finite temperatures, the 2D spectrum is peaked slightly below the diagonal. For $t_2 \gg \tau$ (**Fig3d**), the spectrum is nearly round and the width along the antidiagonal and diagonal are nearly the same.

Relaxation of the lattice by polaron formation shifts the peak towards lower values of E_3 . The peak is still slightly stretched along the diagonal due to static inhomogeneity. Therefore, this model enables the determination of both lattice induced and static line broadening. These simulated spectral dynamics are a clear signature of the overdamped Brownian oscillator; they do not occur for pure homogeneous dephasing and inhomogeneous dephasing.

Fig6a-b show the experimental absorptive CDMS spectra of 18 nm diameter CsPbBr₃ QD at 300K. Spectra are shown at population times, t_2 , of 20 and 800 fs. The scale bars correspond

to normalized change in absorption. These times correspond to spectra prior to and after completion of their line broadening dynamics. There is consistency between the simulations and experiments. This consistency enables the simulations to produce microscopic fluctuation parameters from the experiments^{1, 2, 37, 49}.

Fig6c-d show the diagonal (D) and anti-diagonal (AD) cuts of the CMD spectra and the model, projected onto the E_1 axis. The D and AD projections enable the quantitative evaluation of spectral width and their dynamics. At early times, the AD spectrum is significantly narrower than the D spectrum, as the excitation and detection energies are still highly correlated. The AD profile is nearly Gaussian, though it develops slightly positive wings at very early times. The D spectra prior to relaxation dynamics correspond to the total absorption spectrum. At longer times, the AD spectrum is significantly broadened, and the D spectrum is slightly narrowed. The D spectrum is still broader than the AD spectrum due to static inhomogeneities.

Due to interactions between the quantum exciton and the classical lattice, there will be ensuing dynamics to the D and AD lineshapes. **Fig7a** shows these dynamics in 18 nm diameter CsPbBr₃ QD. Points indicate experimental FWHM, and lines indicate a fit to the Brownian oscillator model with 3 parameters σ, τ, σ_S (**see SI**). The D and AD spectra are parameterized by their FWHM, which are tabulated along with all other parameters in **Table S1 (SI)**.

At initial times, the AD width measures dephasing without size dispersion and without slow lattice fluctuations. It is often considered to be the true homogeneous linewidth, although that only strictly apply in the case of pure dephasing discussed below. It nevertheless provides a measurement of the narrowest linewidth achievable for a material. As population time increases,

the AD width increases with timescale τ due to lattice fluctuations. It settles at value roughly proportional to $2\sqrt{\ln 2} \sigma$. At late times, the difference between the D width and AD linewidth is roughly proportional to σ_S . The analysis of the dynamical AD and D linewidths therefore enable the characterization of the amplitude and timescale which characterize the liquid-like lattice dynamics^{30, 31, 34-38, 49} of a soft lattice, separate from static inhomogeneities.

The experimental observation of spectral dynamics is incompatible with the commonly invoked limit of homogeneous and inhomogeneous lineshapes, in which there are no dynamics⁴⁶. The overdamped Brownian oscillator model reduces to the homogeneous limit when the correlation time is much shorter than the dephasing time, therefore providing a microscopic justification for pure homogeneous dephasing. The lineshape function becomes $g_{\text{fast}}(t) = t/T_2^*$, with $1/T_2^* = \sigma^2\tau/\hbar^2$. However, in that case there are no spectral dynamics and the AD and D widths are constant with time. Our experimental observations therefore clearly demonstrate that the simpler picture of a fixed intrinsic dephasing time does not hold for the dynamically disordered lattice of LHP QDs.

Fig7b shows the size dependent linewidths. The homogeneous linewidth obtained from the AD linewidths at $t_2 = 20$ fs shows no observable size dependence in contrast to expectations from linear spectroscopies^{24, 44, 48, 65, 66}, which reveal larger linewidths for smaller QD with a strong size dependence. The static inhomogeneous broadening is quantified by the D spectra at $t_2 = 20$ fs. The spectra also experience dynamic disorder²⁸⁻³¹, giving rise to Brownian motion of these lineshapes. The AD spectra at $t_2 = 1000$ fs reveal the dynamically broadened total linewidth. Here, the initial linewidth increases in amplitude within 1000 fs with a strong size dependence. Now,

the dynamic inhomogeneous linewidth reveals the origin of the strong size dependence seen in all linear spectroscopies.

Much like T_1 and T_2^* are limits, so are homogeneous and inhomogeneous line broadenings^{1, 2, 3, 37, 46, 49, 50, 79}. The lineshapes are modeled as briefly outlined above and discussed in detail in the **SI**. The parameters are shown in **Fig8**. With these microscopic material parameters obtained by simulations, the experimental observations can be understood. From the experimental data, the homogeneous linewidths are small and size independent. The static inhomogeneous broadening is also size independent and dictated by synthetic quality of the QD^{24, 48}. The strong size dependence to the linewidths of linear absorption and even single QD PL arises from a dynamic inhomogeneous broadening that arises due to their dynamically disordered structural dynamics being overdamped and diffusive.

Conclusions

These CMDS experiments on CsPbBr₃ QD provide the first observation of all contributions to spectral lineshape broadening. Linewidths in the homogeneous limit are revealed to be size independent, a key issue for quantum light sources^{19, 20, 27}. The size dependence to spectral linewidths is revealed to arise from dynamic inhomogeneous broadening due to strong coupling between the quantum excitonic system and the classical phonon bath. Simulations reveal the observed size dependence arises from a complex balance between timescales and amplitudes of lattice fluctuations. Given the first observation and explanation of size dependent line broadening

in LHP QD, a path is paved to engineer their diverse arrays of structures to optimize key processes for photonic applications^{14, 19, 20, 24-27}.

Methods

The methods, materials, and simulations are detailed in the **SI**. Briefly, the CMDS experiments were performed in the pump/probe geometry. The light source was an Ar filled hollow core fiber pumped with an optical parametric amplifier. The coherent pulse trains were generated by acousto-optic modulators. The CMDS experiment has been detailed in our prior works on method development^{83, 85-87} and application of CMDS to QD^{37, 49, 69, 75-81, 88}. The LHP QD were synthesized as described previously^{48, 75, 76, 89, 90}.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supplemental Information (**SI**): Synthesis and characterization of LHP QD, CMDS signal analysis, NAMD theoretical methods.

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Notes

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Author contributions

P.K. supervised the spectroscopy research. M.V.K. supervised the synthesis research. A.G. and P.B. conducted the CMDS experiments. A.G. and S.P. performed the analysis of the CMDS experiments. S.P. performed the simulations. R.T. and D.D. synthesized and characterized the LHP QDs. P.K., S.P., A.G. wrote the manuscript with contributions from all authors.

Fig1. Overview of the lattice structure of lead-halide perovskite (LHP) quantum dots (QD) as a springboard to thinking about spectral lineshapes and their dynamics. a) Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) image of representative LHP QD. b) Edge length distribution of LHP QD in an ensemble. c) Illustration of the lattice of CsPbBr₃ LHP QD. d) Illustration of the lattice undergoing a polaronic distortion about a central charge.

Fig2. Optical spectra reveal size dependent linewidths. a) The linear absorption and photoluminescence (PL) spectra of CsPbBr₃ QD of edge lengths 20 and 5.9 nm. b) The dependence of the PL linewidth upon QD edge length.

Fig3. A time domain view of spectral lineshapes to move from statics to dynamics. a) The radiated signal field (polarization) under three limits of lineshape broadening mechanisms of homogeneous broadening (blue), homogeneous and static inhomogeneous broadening (orange), and homogeneous with dynamic spectral diffusion (green). b) The corresponding lineshapes under these conditions. c) Model two level system with exciton energy ΔE_{X1} . Dephasing arises due to population relaxation ($1/T_1$) and dynamical fluctuations $\delta E(t)$. d) An illustration of the dynamics that take place in a fluctuating, diffusively evolving lattice such as LHP QD.

Fig4. Lineshapes dynamics in ensembles are unraveled by coherent multi-dimensional spectroscopy (CMDS). a) A time domain representation of energy fluctuations in single dots (colored), averaging to a time correlation function for the ensemble of QD (black). $C(t)$ was scaled for clarity. b) For given initial conditions, the distribution of transition energy shift towards the average and broaden. c) These fluctuations and correlations are directly measured by CMDS, schematically illustrated.

Fig5. Spectral diffusion in one-dimensional and two-dimensional spectra. a) Illustration of an ensemble 1D spectrum (black) which is comprised of an inhomogeneous distribution of homogeneous spectra. The schematic is shown prior to spectral diffusion. b) The same 1D spectrum after spectral diffusion. c) The 2D CMDS spectrum simulated prior to relaxation as discussed in the text. d) The 2D CMDS spectrum after relaxation. The amplitude is the normalized change in absorbance.

Fig6. CMDS experiments reveal spectral diffusion. a) The absorptive CMDS spectrum measured prior to relaxation as discussed in the text. b) The CMDS spectrum measured after relaxation. Data is shown for CsPbBr₃ QD of 18 nm edge length, at 300 K. c) – d) The Diagonal (D) and Anti-Diagonal (AD) projections at the two corresponding population times. The amplitude is the normalized change in absorbance.

Fig7. Linewidths are both dynamic and carry size dependence. a) The full width at half maximum (FWHM) for the D and AD projections for 18 nm edge length CsPbBr₃ QD reveals time dependence on the femtosecond timescale. The arrows reflect the amount of dynamic (red) and static (black) broadening revealed by CMDs. b) The dependence of various linewidths upon the edge length.

Fig8. Multi-Mode Brownian Oscillator model parameters. a) the fluctuation rate constant. b)

The static and dynamic contributions to the linewidths.

TOC image

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